

THE STATE OF THE ANTIOXIDANT DEFENSE SYSTEM IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS C

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Annotation: Informative markers of iron metabolism in patients with chronic viral hepatitis C (HCV) have been studied in comparison with healthy individuals. It has been established that the phenomenon of iron overload is observed in this category of patients. The indicator of antioxidant activity of blood serum in patients with HCV is significantly reduced compared with the indicators in healthy individuals. The revealed changes may indicate a violation of the balance of pro- and antioxidant processes, which plays an important role in the pathogenesis of the disease.

Key words: markers, Chronic viral hepatitis C, status of iron, antioxidant activity, serum of blood.

Iron is a ubiquitous and necessary element for all living things, it is the main component of the synthesis of hemoglobin and myoglobin, supports the pro-oxidant-antioxidant balance, catalyzes the processes of electron transport, etc.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the total pool of body iron in an adult male weighing 70 kg.

Table 1.

Component	mg	%
Hemoglobin	2300	60 – 65
Ferritin	500 – 550	12 – 15
Hemosiderin	500 – 550	12 – 15
Myoglobin	230 – 280	8 – 9
Cytochromes, catalase	100	3 – 5
Transferrin Iron	3	0.1 – 0.2
Total	3500 – 4000	100

As can be seen from the table below, the largest amount of iron is found in hemoglobin. The exchange of iron in the body itself is a set of multidirectional processes-its absorption in the gastrointestinal tract, its entry into the bloodstream, its binding here by a specific protein transferrin, the transport of iron as part of the transferrin-iron complex into target tissues, where it is used in the synthesis of numerous iron-binding proteins, the storage of iron in the intracellular protein ferritin, as well as in hemosiderin, iron reutilization from the depot, reuse and excretion of iron. The main regulator of iron metabolism in the body is the iron-binding, iron-transport protein transferrin, which is normally saturated with iron by about 30%. Disorders in iron metabolism are usually manifested by its deficiency, iron deficiency syndrome, however, an equally important problem is iron overload syndrome, which can be caused by hereditary forms of hemochromatosis, hereditary hemolytic anemia (thalassemia), nutritional iron overload, chronic liver diseases (hepatitis B and C, alcoholic liver disease, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis). Excess iron leads to a significant increase in the content of intracellular and plasma ferritin, as well as hemosiderin, excess iron initiates free radical processes,

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since iron is a catalyst for oxidative processes at the level of important biomolecules such as DNA, lipids, carbohydrates. At the same time, the etiology of iron metabolism disorders that occur in HCV is not entirely clear, either there is a primary hepatopathy caused by the virus and, as a result, an increase in iron content in intracellular ferritin, or there is a primary accumulation of iron in hepatocytes, which exacerbates secondary liver damage caused by the virus.

The aim of the work was to study the iron status and antioxidant activity of blood serum in patients with chronic viral hepatitis C (HCV) in a comparative aspect with healthy individuals.

Materials and methods of research. 30 patients with HCV of both sexes aged from 24 to 50 years (average age -34.2 ± 2.2 l.) were examined. The study also included 30 conditionally healthy individuals aged 22 to 42 years in the control group (average age-31.2 years). The diagnosis of HCV was made on the basis of a clinical examination and the results of laboratory and instrumental studies. HCV markers in blood serum were determined by enzyme immunoassay. Serum iron levels were determined by the bathophenanthroline method from markers of iron status, serum transferrin levels were analyzed by the Mancini radial diffusion immunochemical method, and serum ferritin levels were analyzed by turbidimetry on a HITACHI-902 biochemical analyzer (Japan) using commercial Ferritin kits from Roche (Switzerland). The antioxidant activity of the serum was determined by the rate of accumulation of malonic dialdehyde in lipids under the action of the oxidant Fe^{3+} . Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program. The Student's unpaired t-test was used to determine the statistical significance of the differences depending on the distribution parameters.

Results and discussion. The examined patients complained of weakness, fatigue, and decreased working capacity. A physical examination revealed minor hepatomegaly in all the examined patients. The activity of transaminases in the majority of the examined patients was within the physiological norm, in 9 patients this indicator was higher than normal. Indicators of the iron status in the body are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Indicators of iron status in the control group and in the group of patients with HCV

Surveyed	Serum iron mmol/L	Transferrin serum, g/l	CST,%	Serum ferritin, ng/ml
Control (n -30)	24.1 ± 1.6	3.10 ± 0.02	28.2 ± 0.78	104.3 ± 12.6
Patients with HCV (n-30)	38.2 ± 0.8	2.15 ± 0.03	69.4 ± 1.0	875.6 ± 22.4
r	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

As can be seen from Table 1, in the control group (healthy individuals), the serum iron level averaged 24.1 ± 1.6 mmol/l, and the average transferrin level, the main carrier of this iron in the bloodstream, was 3.10 ± 0.02 g/l. Calculations show that with such ferrokinetic parameters, saturation of the total transferrin pool averages $28.2 \pm 0.78\%$, which ensures normal iron turnover between the plasma iron pool and the functional bone marrow iron pool and, consequently, physiological hematopoiesis in the bone marrow. The serum ferritin level averages 104.3 ± 12.6 ng/ml in the healthy individuals we examined. Considering that there is a direct quantitative correlation between the level of serum ferritin and total iron reserves in the body, which is expressed in the fact that the serum

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ferritin content of 1 ng/ml quantitatively corresponds to 10 mg of elemental iron, it was noted that the average iron reserves in the examined amount to 1,043 g of iron.

The study of iron status indicators in the group of patients with HCV showed that almost all (89%) of the examined patients with HCV have characteristic changes in markers of the body's iron status. Thus, the examined patients with HCV have the phenomenon of hyperferremia, the serum iron content in such patients is on average 38.2 ± 0.8 mmol/l, which is significantly higher than in the control group ($p < 0.001$, 1.6 times higher than in the control group. Hyperferremia occurs against the background of severe hypotransferrinemia. So, on average, the transferrin level in the blood serum of the examined patients is only 2.15 ± 0.03 g/l, which is 1.4 times less than the same indicator in the control ($p < 0.001$). Against the background of severe hyperferremia and hypotransferrinemia, the saturation of the total transferrin pool with iron increases significantly, on average, the iron saturation coefficient of transferrin is $69.4 \pm 1.0\%$, which is 2.5 times higher than in the control ($p < 0.001$). The phenomenon of iron overload in the body of patients with HCV is also indicated by hyperferritinemia, on average, the serum ferritin level in patients with HCV is 875.6 ± 22.4 ng/ml, which is 8.4 times higher than in the control group ($p < 0.001$). In quantitative terms, therefore, the total iron reserves in the body of the examined patients amount to 8,756 g of elemental iron.

Analysis of the indicator of antioxidant activity in the blood serum of patients with HCV showed that there is a phenomenon of a decrease in this indicator in their comparative aspect with the control group – 1.09 ± 0.15 con.units 1.89 ± 0.1 con. units, respectively ($p < 0.001$). There were no direct correlations between the indicators of the iron status in the body of the examined patients with HCV and the indicators of their antioxidant activity.

Conclusions.

It was revealed that in patients with HCV, the iron status in the body is characterized by laboratory signs of iron overload-hyperferremia, hypotransferrinemia, increased iron saturation coefficient and severe hyperferritinemia. The antioxidant activity of blood serum in patients with HCV is reduced in comparison with the norm.

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